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PROSPECTS FOR IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF HUMAN RESOURCES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The prospects for improving the efficiency of human capital in Uzbekistan lie in the economic development of entrepreneurship and the social modernization of education. These factors are essential for building a prosperous society centered on human dignity and well-being. Enhancing human capital is seen as a strategic priority that contributes to national development, innovation, and long-term sustainability.

Key words: Human capital, education, potential, innovation, society, human resources, management, development, reform, modernization.

Annotatsiya: O'zbekistonda inson kapitalining samaradorligini oshirish istiqbollari tadbirkorlikni iqtisodiy rivojlantirish va ta'limni ijtimoiy modernizatsiya qilish bilan chambarchas bog'liqdir. Ushbu omillar farovonlikka yo'naltirilgan, inson qadriyatlariga asoslangan jamiyatni shakllantirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Inson kapitalini rivojlantirish davlat taraqqiyoti, innovatsiyalar va barqarorlikning strategik yo'nalishlaridan biri sifatida qaralmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: Inson kapitali, ta'lim, salohiyat, innovatsiya, jamiyat, inson resurslari, boshqaruv, rivojlanish, islohot, modernizatsiya.

Аннотация: Перспективы повышения эффективности человеческого капитала в Узбекистане связаны с экономическим развитием предпринимательства и социальной модернизацией системы образования. Эти факторы играют ключевую роль в построении процветающего общества, основанного на уважении человеческого достоинства и благополучия. Развитие человеческого капитала рассматривается как стратегический приоритет, способствующий национальному прогрессу, инновациям и устойчивому развитию.

Ключевые слова: Человеческий капитал, образование, потенциал, инновации, общество, человеческие ресурсы, управление, развитие, реформа, модернизация.

INTRODUCTION

At the new stage of Uzbekistan's development, the improvement of human resources is of urgent importance. Because the development of society directly depends on the efficiency of human capital. Our current era is characterized by the transition of the world's leading countries to the "Fourth Industrial Revolution", "Smart Economy", "Innovative Economy".[2] In order to respond to such changes in society, it is necessary to improve the methods of achieving goals by increasing human capital and adapting to current conditions. Therefore, in society, they should encourage creativity and innovation in people, because there will be no changes in society without creative initiative. The researchers' opinion about the reason for this is as follows: "People are developing a sense of responsibility in solving their own problems, and the relationship of carelessness towards the state is being cut off. Citizens' way of life and their social behavior are significantly influenced by national and modern ethical and moral values and standards".[3] It is important for people to have an important place in the society and to demonstrate their potential.

LITERATURE REVIEW

We see that the beginnings of developed societies were similar to the changes in today's Uzbek society. For example, Adam Smith writes about the value of knowledge of workers, recognizing their skill and influence on the efficiency of any company. Furthermore, Adam Smith stated: "Education is a form of investment in human beings that supports skilled and trained workers. Empowering employees, as well as giving them the opportunity to make decisions, increases their motivation and reduces their resistance to organizational changes,[4] he says. The use of human capital, ensuring its direct efficiency and the income from its use will also be relevant for society. Because regardless of the sources of capital formation, the person himself has its benefits for the society or the state.

It should be noted that the efficiency of human capital activity and the level of income from its use as prospects for improving the efficiency of human resources are determined by individual interests, preferences and values, and the cultural level of the subject. Accordingly, the capabilities of users of human capital require the formation of its motivational mechanism. This is the value of human capital in society and the value of its level of ownership income. By developing entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan, ample opportunities are being

created to reduce unemployment and increase the potential and capital of entrepreneurs. On December 23, 2021, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev adopted the Law “On Establishing the Day of Entrepreneurs”[5]. Accordingly, August 20 of every year was designated as Entrepreneurs’ Day. This means that it is possible to move towards development by using the intellectual potential of entrepreneurs in the society. Accordingly, in the conditions of the modern economy, special requirements are placed on knowledge, they must ensure the possibility of introducing new technologies, including innovative technologies. Therefore, the main driving force of socio-economic development as a society is the capital of entrepreneurs. In general, the growth of entrepreneurship is more effective for society and the state than ever before.

Business activity in the modern economic environment largely depends on their scientific potential and capital. Currently, in our opinion, in most developed societies, sufficient attention is paid to the formation of a healthy competitive environment and the working conditions of people. As a result, as a result of their activity, the effectiveness of human capital is being highlighted in a positive way for the state and society. It can be said that human capital is becoming an important resource for society.

The triad is the basis of the Finnish labor market model. He is three consists of the most important component: labor and organizations with the capital located at the base of the triangle, at its apex and the government is located. This is a triangular labor market the strategic triad of decision-making during negotiations organizes. In the strategic triangle of the triad, the employer, The workers and the government jointly make a strategic choice increase, [6] - he says.

In Uzbekistan, it is very important to increase the return on investment of entrepreneurs as prospects for improving the efficiency of human resources. In this regard, President Shavkat Mirziyoev said, “I propose to strengthen in the Constitution that entrepreneurs have the right to carry out any activity not prohibited by law, to independently choose the directions of their activity, to receive unlimited income from entrepreneurship. The state must provide a favorable business and investment environment and conditions for the development of private entrepreneurship, protect free and fair competition, and guarantee that monopolization in economic activity will not be allowed”. [7] In our opinion, by creating opportunities for entrepreneurship, an opportunity is created for the manifestation of human capital in the society through entrepreneurial activities. Freedom in society is a great opportunity for an entrepreneur to demonstrate his potential.

As a result of studying the research on the prospects of improving the efficiency of human resources, it is known that in the research conducted by the foreign philosopher Guest[8], it can be observed that various indices have been introduced to measure the dimensions and characteristics of human capital. In particular, it examines sales and purchases as financial indicators, goods and services as performance indices, customer services, number of errors, customer satisfaction, etc. This leads to the study of the criteria of attracting new knowledge, integration, competence, human power diagram and its rational use as factors indicating the effectiveness of human capital. As a result, integration processes between cost, time, quantity, quality, strategic criteria, fair working conditions, satisfaction of people’s needs, ability skills, competence and investments create factors such as interpersonal cooperation in the management of society, knowledge, income per capita[9] . According to another scientist, S.A. Kurgansky, the perspective of the effectiveness of human capital in his opinion: “The set of knowledge, skills and other qualities formed as a result of investments and savings by individuals, if they are used appropriately, will create a new value and income stream.” [10] points out.

According to research, since it is new in human resources, it is increasingly used in organizations with strategic importance. This means that human capital plays an important role in improving people’s development, life and income, increasing knowledge, skills and production potential, economic growth and reducing poverty. As new revolutions take place in the world’s struggle against capitalism, human power will be more important than ever. In our view, future research on human capital, based on recent economic revolutions, will focus on two goals, namely, measuring gaps in human capital and exploring how human capital can lead to greater productivity and profitability.

Prospects for improving the efficiency of human resources in Uzbekistan would be appropriate if they were expressed in terms of their management. Because human capital is currently considered a process of strategic importance for the state. As stated in the Decree No. PF-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026”, “Goal 52: To improve the position of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the global index and enter the top 50 countries by 2030”. [1] this is achieved primarily by improving human capital.

DISCUSSION

In our opinion, human resource management is an innovative approach to human resource demand, treating people as assets (human capital) whose current value can be measured and whose future value can be increased through investment. A state or society that implements human capital management spends its

future on clearly defining and continuously monitoring expected results. From an entrepreneurial perspective, it is manifested in the appropriate evaluation and reward of human capital to achieve business goals, create innovations and support their continuous improvement. Perspectives of the effectiveness of human capital are the establishment of effective labor relations, its support represents the knowledge of personnel and its values. At the same time, it is also important that labor relations are managed to ensure legal compliance and that the knowledge key to society's success is protected.

RESULTS

In the new stage of development, attention is paid at the level of state policy to the processes that are the basis for the development of human capital as a result of recent reforms in our country. In particular, if we pay attention to non-governmental educational organizations, if in 2017 there were up to 5 thousand educational organizations, by the end of 2020 their number will exceed 14 thousand.[11] Also, 2.5 million children between the ages of 3 and 7 are included in the system of the Ministry of Preschool Education. The number of educational institutions in the republic is 6,154, of which 5,586 are state-owned, and 568 are non-state educational institutions. This corresponds to the increase of state and non-state educational structures in the education system of our country, their mutual competition, opportunities for choice for citizens, and the improvement of the quality of education, thereby improving human capital.

In the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026: "It is aimed to reach 50% coverage level with higher education and increase the quality of education, according to which "increasing admission parameters in 2022 based on the proposals of personnel customers, in 2022 the coverage level of youth with higher education to 38% delivery, introduction of the procedure for independent determination of admission parameters by higher education institutions on the basis of a fee-contract, to increase the admission rate to at least 250 thousand in 2026, to give academic and financial independence to state higher education institutions, including payment of wages by them, the number of employees, establishing the practice of independent determination of the amount of the payment contract and the form of education, clearly defining the relevant rights and powers of the state higher education institutions" [1]. In our opinion, this is the future that determines the effectiveness of human capital for the society, increasing the competitiveness of science and education, increasing the training of personnel with scientific potential.

CONCLUSION

The most important factor of human resources is that human intelligence is significantly different from others and it requires a special approach. Forming a personnel policy for its implementation and regularly improving it is a promising direction of the efficiency of human capital in society. Because a company or society with strong, experienced and committed personnel can gain leadership and achieve success.

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